

Ethics and Gender Equality issues

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3	CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique CNRS	France
4	UT	Université de Tours	France
5	MF	Mezzo Forte	France
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7	Hangvető	Hangvető Zenei Terjeszto Tarsulaskorlatolt Felelossegu Tarsasag	Hungary
8	GEOFolkLife	GEORGIA Folk Life	Georgia
9	3DR	3D Research Srl	Italy
10	SD	S.D. Cinematografica	Italy
11	PK/CUT	Politechnika Krakowska	Poland
12	COBO	Comune di Bologna	Italy
13	BCM-BGIR	Ministero della Cultura	Italy
14	MdV	Museo del Violino	Italy

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CCIs	Cultural and Creative Industries
CH	Cultural Heritage
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
ECHOES	European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science project
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HLPF	High Level Political Forum
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This report is part of the output from Task 1.6 Ethical and Gender Equality issues. This task objective is to ensure that all appropriate ethical standards are met, concurrently monitoring project activities for the potential emergence of any areas of concern regarding gender or ethics. The Project Coordinator assisted by the Project Manager will be monitoring potential issues among the project partners throughout the lifetime of the project.

Document History

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Introduction

The present deliverable *D1.7 Ethics and Gender Equality issues* aims at guiding the research activities of the project in respecting key ethical research principles. This document outlines the framework through which the project ensures that all activities are implemented in accordance with recognised principles of research ethics and in full compliance with gender equality and non-discrimination requirements, the *Do No Significant Harm* (DNSH) principle, and the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The project activities are not likely to raise major ethics issues, as also stated in the ethics self-assessment produced within the project proposal.

Intended as a living document, it will have a second release at M17 with *D1.8 Final version of EGEP* to reflect the evolving activities of the project.

1. General principles of Ethics Management in PlaceMUS XR

As stated in the introduction of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, “*research is the quest for knowledge obtained through systematic study, thinking, observation, and experimentation... to increase our understanding of ourselves and the world in which we live*” (...)¹

To be trusted and credible, research needs to have as its fundamentals some principles of integrity, that the Code of Conduct² identifies as:

- **Reliability** in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, methodology, analysis, and use of resources.
- **Honesty** in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting, and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full, and unbiased way.
- **Respect** for colleagues, research participants, research subjects, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment.

¹ ALLEA (2023) The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – Revised Edition 2023. Berlin. DOI 10.26356/ECOC, p. 3

² *Ibid.*, p. 5

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- **Accountability** for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision, and mentoring, and for its wider societal impacts.

The PlaceMUS XR project adopts these principles, committing itself to carrying out its activities in this spirit and also establishing a monitoring system within the project activities for its entire duration in this direction.

2. Regulatory framework for Ethics Management in PlaceMUS XR

Ethics issues in PlaceMUS XR are regulated by the following:

Grant Agreement 101233325

- Article 13.1 - Sensitive information
- Article 14 - *Ethics*
- Article 30 - Payment Suspension
- Article 31 - Grant Agreement Suspension
- Annex 5 - Specific Rules for Article 14

In particular, Article 14.1 - *Ethics* of the GA states that “*the action must be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles*” and Article 14.2 – *Values* states that “*the beneficiaries must commit to and ensure the respect of basic EU values (such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities)*”.

Furthermore, Annex 5 - Specific Rules for Article 14 states that “*the beneficiaries must carry out the action in compliance with:*

- *ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity)*

and

- *applicable EU, international and national law, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols*”.

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Also, it states that “*the beneficiaries must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action and, where applicable, in line with the gender equality plan. They must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level.*”

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR)

3. Ethics Issues

Having as its funding principle Article 13 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union stating that “*The arts and scientific research shall be free of constraint. Academic freedom shall be respected*”³, PlaceMUS XR commitment with integrity in the conduct of research will be reflected in promoting high quality standards, reliability through accurate design, methodology, analysis and transparency on how data are collected, analysed, shared.

The Consortium commits also in strictly monitoring that research misconduct and other unacceptable practices, such as fabrication, falsification, or plagiarism in proposing, performing, or reviewing research, or in reporting research results, are prevented, detected and deterred.

In line with The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, the Consortium acknowledges that negative results can be as relevant as positive findings for publication and dissemination.

3.1 Ethics dimension in the PlaceMUS XR Consortium

All the public bodies (Universities and Research Institutions) in the PlaceMUS XR consortium have an Ethics Department whose purpose is to foster reflection on the ethical aspects raised by research practice, its challenges and its relationship with society, to raise awareness among researchers and staff of the importance of ethics and to provide training on research ethics and integrity.

³ Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, 2012 O.J. (C 326) 391.

3.2 Project related ethics issues

The project will comply with Article 14.1 of the GA, ensuring that the action will be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols.

The PlaceMUS XR results have an **exclusive** focus on **civil applications** and do not envisage dual use potential risks, as they have no applications in the military sector nor have the potential to create negative consequences for health and safety, agriculture, the environment or national/international security.

All project activities and outputs will be planned and implemented in alignment with the highest standards on gender equality and non-discrimination. The project will ensure equal and inclusive participation by actively preventing any form of discrimination based on gender, ethnicity, religion, language, national origin or socioeconomic background for all participants and stakeholder.

Personal data

Following the requests of the GA and Article 5 of the DGPR, personal data within the project will be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes that will be clearly shared with the people involved and not processed for different purposes, processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner, adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed.

WP5 and WP6 foresee a set of surveys. These include preliminary surveys addressed to members of the PlaceMUS XR consortium, museum curators, cultural and creative industries (CCIs) professionals, scholars, educators, students, and the general public. They also include verification surveys aimed at assessing the developed tools, proposed scenarios, and the overall user experience regarding interaction, usability, accessibility, usefulness, and overall satisfaction, as well as identifying and addressing potential critical issues. Users' participation in surveys is voluntary. Participants will sign informed consent forms detailing the research purpose, methods, risks, and benefits, data use and storage. Personal data of interviewees will be used exclusively for statistical and research

Ethics and Gender Equality issues purposes pertaining to the PlaceMUS XR project and will in all cases be aggregated and anonymised. Data will be reviewed for consistency and inaccuracies will be corrected or removed; participants may request corrections. No personal data will be transferred to external organizations. Personal data will be securely stored on GDPR compliant servers, accessible only to authorized personnel and they will be deleted after a period of 6 months from the end of the project. They will not be migrated to ECCCH.

Photos and videos will be used to create contents, dissemination material, on the web page and, sometimes, in deliverables. Informed consent (see the example in Annex I) will be obtained by asking the individuals concerned to sign a specific form which will require not only authorisation to use their image, but also the scope of authorization, the purpose of the research activity, terms and conditions (duration, geographic scope, compensation, rights, withdrawal, privacy).

A dedicated contact in the relevant section of the project webpage will allow to report issues and manage/withdraw consent.

FAIR Data

As better defined and detailed in D1.5 - Data Management Plan, PlaceMUS XR will manage its data and metadata in line with the FAIR principles, ensuring that they will be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable, with the dual purpose of improving the impact of research and its efficiency (avoiding duplication of effort and encouraging the reuse of results).

Non-EU Countries in PlaceMUS XR

Some of the project activities will be carried out in a non-EU country, namely Georgia. Georgia has been associated to Horizon 2020 since 2016 and to Horizon Europe since January 2021. The activities undertaken in Georgia do not raise potential ethics issues. One of the project case studies will be a **Journey Through Georgian Polyphonic Traditions**, aimed at promoting and preserving Georgian polyphonic music as a vital part of the country's cultural heritage and to experience performances and traditional songs by local folk ensembles in their context. Recognized by UNESCO as masterpiece of oral and intangible heritage, this musical

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tradition acts as a bridge between East and West, embodying Georgia's distinctive role at the crossroads of diverse cultures and musical traditions.

On 1 March 2024 the New Law of Georgia on Personal Data Protection has entered into force, aligning the national legislation with the GDPR and allowing the project to ensure the same level of data protection applied in the other EU countries.

4. Gender

The United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) n. 5 is to “Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls” and is the concept underlying this section. The “Progress on the Sustainable Development Goals: The Gender Snapshot 2025”⁴ reports that, in spite of the significant effort and advancements, gender equality is far from being achieved and the previous edition, the “Progress on the Sustainable Development Goals: The Gender Snapshot 2024” points out how an increased access to upper-secondary education, especially in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) could create huge opportunities for young women and girls and boost economic development. In leading economies, women currently make up only 26 per cent of the workforce in data and artificial intelligence and 12 per cent in cloud computing⁵. To tackle this situation, the 2025 UN HLPF Thematic Review Expert Group during its meeting identified, among the policies and actions to maximize synergies, mitigate trade-offs and drive transformation, the following: 1) expanding women's participation in the technological future; 2) ensure participatory data collection and policymaking; 3) expand access to STEM education for women and girls and improve digital literacy for women of all ages; 4) foster women's leadership in technology⁶.

⁴ UN Women and DESA. 2025. Progress on the Sustainable Development Goals: The Gender Snapshot 2025. New York: UN Women and DESA. © UN Women and United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Statistics Division

⁵ UN-Women and DESA. 2024. Progress on the Sustainable Development Goals: The Gender Snapshot 2024. New York: UN-Women and DESA.

⁶ https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2025-04/SDG%205%20EGM%20Summary%20Report_0.pdf

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The PlaceMUS XR project commits to addressing gender inequalities at all stages of its implementation, promoting full inclusivity both within the Consortium and in relation to its outcomes.

4.1 Gender balance in the PlaceMUS XR Consortium

Gender balance within the project is one of the main issues addressed when considering the project composition, and it has been ensured that women are largely represented in the distribution of roles of responsibility.

Having a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) in place is now an eligibility criterion for certain categories of legal entities, namely public bodies (including e.g. ministries, research funding organisations, municipalities, as well as public-for-profit organisations such as certain museums), research organisations (both public and private) and higher education establishments (both public and private) from EU countries and non-EU countries associated to Horizon Europe⁷.

Six out of the 11 PlaceMUS XR beneficiaries are public bodies whose Institutions have adopted a Gender Equality Plan (GEP). One of the private sector partners, namely Beneficiary 9 - 3D Research, has also adopted⁸ a Gender Equality Management System (SGPG) in compliance with UNI/PdR125:2022, targeting mainly the gender pay gap, the prevention and contrast of gender-based violence and the implementation of external projects aimed at encouraging young women to pursue their aspirations, with a particular focus on raising awareness of technical and scientific disciplines (i.e. STEM disciplines), and more generally in fields where women are under-represented or absent.

In line with Annex 5 - Specific Rules for Article 14, measures have been taken within the project Consortium to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action and in the starting phase of the activities the PlaceMUS XR team is composed of around 60 researchers from 6 countries and 11 Institution, both public and private, with a gender structure of **49% male and 51% female**.

⁷ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Gender equality plans (GEPs) – Frequently asked questions – Updated, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/8938328>

⁸ <https://www.3dresearch.it/it/varie-it/parita-di-genere/>

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This is also reflected in the project governance, as the Project Coordinator and Project Manager are female as well as **9 out of 15 WP Leaders** (composing also the project Executive Board).

4.2 Project related gender issues

No evidence has been identified to date of gender-related disparities in the design, production, or engagement with PlaceMUS XR experiences, nor in the utilisation of interactive tools, participation in training activities, or the subsequent exploitation of project results. Furthermore, the project explicitly aims to promote heightened awareness of gender bias among both internal stakeholders and external audiences, with the broader objective of fostering greater participation of girls and young women in relevant professional and educational trajectories. This objective will be implemented through a series of concrete and targeted measures intended to cultivate an inclusive environment in which all individuals are enabled to realise their full potential and are safeguarded against any form of discrimination.

Finally, within the surveys planned in WP5 and WP6, the gender dimension—both in research and in educational contexts—will be systematically considered, alongside other pertinent ethical issues, as outlined in detail in Deliverable D5.1 Preliminary Survey: Objectives, Methodologies, and Tools.

5. Artificial Intelligence

The project Consortium is fully aware of the ethic issue related to the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI), mainly as regards its environmental impact, copyright issues, bias originating from stereotypical representations related to gender, ethnicity, religion, language, national origin and socioeconomic conditions.

AI technologies will be employed within the PlaceMUS XR project in selected activities to support multilingual translation, text-to-speech generation, and the automatic or semi-automatic adaptation of textual content for different audiences, including children. Their use is specifically foreseen under Task 4.2 – *Accessibility-oriented AI*, which aims to investigate, pilot, and implement AI-based methods to enhance the accessibility and inclusiveness of textual and audio resources.

Within Task 4.2, the project will examine and apply AI-supported procedures for:

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- (i) multilingual translation workflows, including the production of accessible formats such as Braille;
- (ii) linguistic optimization and adaptation of register, complexity, and formality; and
- (iii) experimental evaluation of text-to-speech technologies and virtual sign-language avatars.

AI may also be used, where appropriate, to generate visual materials intended to illustrate abstract concepts, communicate complex ideas, or depict historical contexts. In all cases, the use of AI-generated or AI-assisted outputs will be clearly stated in the corresponding metadata and openly disclosed in all resources made available to the public, in line with EU principles on transparency, traceability, and responsible AI use.

6. Inclusiveness and Accessibility

A whole Work Package, namely WP4 - **Accessibility of Media and Tools**, is dedicated to promoting accessibility and social inclusion of all citizens, including those with special needs, in museums and online to the ECCCH and to test AI potentialities to improve accessibility. Objective 06 of PlaceMUS XR is to **create and promote accessible solutions for extended interaction with places of Music** with the following expected results:

- **R 06.1 Accessibility of contents and media**, also through the support of Artificial Intelligence (AI) (multilanguage translation, text to speech, experimental virtual avatars in Sign Language, automatic/semi-automatic text optimization for different audience and age groups, included children).
- **R 06.2 Accessibility of developed tools' functionalities and GUI** (graphic user interface).
- **R 06.3 Haptic tool for accessible engagement with Rhythm** in museum context (including deaf people).
- **R 06.4 Gestural tool for accessible engagement with Harmony** in museum (including physically disabilities).
- **R 06.5 Tools for synesthetic single and multi-user experiences with tuning**, in museum (including deaf people).

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A principle that will be followed is not to come out with niche solutions but rather with innovative solutions that offer an added value to the general audience too and offer an enhanced experience.

- **R 06.6** The action **“Multisensory, representation of information sets”** is built on: 1) visual mapping of acoustic data (from sound to graphics), 2) acoustic mapping of visual data (from architecture, history, context to sounds).

In addition, Universal Design (UD) principles, i.e. Equitable Use, Flexibility in Use, Simple and Intuitive Use, Perceptible Information, Tolerance for Error, Low Physical Effort, Size and Space for Approach and Use, will be applied in the design of dissemination material, storytelling and interactive tools.

7. Fair remuneration

PlaceMUS XR includes the production of digital dataset related to Itineraries and Scenarios. In particular, Task 7.6 *Audio-visual storytelling* aims at multimedia content integration, coming both from archives and created from scratch. This includes sound and video recording of musical performances (2-3 live performances with musicians, max duration 5' each one) involving Music Schools and professional Ensemble.

The project acknowledges the importance the work of music performers and their entitlement to receive appropriate and proportionate remuneration, as also stated in EU Directive 2019/790⁹ and has a dedicated budget aimed at covering related costs.

8. Conclusions

According to the analysis carried out so far, the PlaceMUS XR project does not raise critical ethics issues and has been designed considering both gender issues and the main ethical challenges identified so far.

This does not mean that potential ethics or gender threats will not arise in the future. The commitment of the project Consortium and the aim of Task 1.6 are

⁹ Directive (EU) 2019/790 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC (Text with EEA relevance.) PE/51/2019/REV/1 OJ L 130, 17.5.2019, pp. 92–125

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precisely to ensure that such potential issues are identified and mitigated promptly and in the most appropriate manner. Dedicated instruments aimed at this monitoring are being developed and will be used as self-assessment tools within every project activity.

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